

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10278835

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TO COMPARE 0.25% ROPIVACAINE AND 0.25% BUPIVACAINE IN TAP BLOCK FOR POSTOPERATIVE ANALGESIA IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING ABDOMINAL SURGERIES.

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ABSTRACT INTRODUCTION

Pain has been defined as an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage or described in terms of such damage.¹ Pain is the most dreaded problem which a person fears after any surgery.

The transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block is an anaesthesia technique that provides analgesia to the parietal peritoneum as well as the skin and muscles of the anterior abdominal wall.⁴ Since the thoracolumbar nerves originating from the T6 to L1 spinal roots run into this plane and supply sensory nerves to the anterolateral abdominal wall⁵, the local anaesthetic spread in this plane can block the neural afferents and provide analgesia to the anterolateral abdominal wall.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim of study was to compare 0.25% Ropivacaine and 0.25% Bupivacaine in TAP block for postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing Abdominal Surgeries.

The following parameters were compared:

- To study the effectiveness of transverses abdominis plane block for post-operative analgesia in Abdominal Surgeries.
- To compare the duration of analgesia and its effectiveness conferred by 0.25% Ropivacaine and 0.25% Bupivacaine.
- Total requirement of rescue analgesia.
- To watch for occurrence of side effects, if any

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A comparative clinical study was carried out on 60 adult patients belonging to ASA grade I or II, scheduled for elective Abdominal Surgeries.

All patients were administered spinal anaesthesia with bupivacaine heavy 0.5%, 2.0-4.0 ml with 25 G spinal needle at L2-L3 or L3-L4 vertebral interspace. The patients were randomly allocated in two groups and study drug was injected at the end of surgery according to the group. The volume of administered drug kept constant (20 ml).

Group I: Patients received TAP BLOCK on each side with 10ml 0.25% Ropivacaine.

Group II: Patients received TAP BLOCK on each side with 10ml 0.25% Bupivacaine.

CONCLUSION

Transversus Abdominis Plane Block (TAP Block) provides better postoperative analgesia in various abdominal surgeries. 0.25% ropivacaine and 0.25% bupivacaine are equally effective in TAP block and provides effective postoperative analgesia but ropivacaine group shown longer duration of action compared to bupivacaine which was statistically significant without causing any increased adverse effects.

KEYWORDS

Postoperative analgesia, abdominal surgeries, TAP block

INTRODUCTION

Pain has been defined as an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage or described in terms of such damage.¹ Pain is the most dreaded problem which a person fears after any surgery.

Abdominal wall blocks are performed on the principle of high-volume local anaesthetic deposition within a fascial plane.² Ultrasound-guided performances with constant visualisation of the needle increases the accuracy of placement and reduces inadvertent visceral or neurovascular injury.³

The transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block is an anaesthesia technique that provides analgesia to the parietal peritoneum as well as the skin and muscles of the anterior abdominal wall.⁴ Since the thoracolumbar nerves originating from the T6 to L1 spinal roots run into this plane and supply sensory nerves to the anterolateral abdominal wall⁵, the local anaesthetic spread in this plane and block the neural afferents and provide analgesia to the anterolateral abdominal wall. The transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block was first introduced by Rafi⁶ in 2001 as a landmark-guided technique via the triangle of Petit to achieve a field block.

Hence in this study we had compared the efficacy of 0.25% Ropivacaine and 0.25% Bupivacaine 10ml each side in bilateral TAP block for postoperative pain management in patients undergoing below umbilical surgery.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To compare 0.25% Ropivacaine and 0.25% Bupivacaine in TAP block for postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing Abdominal Surgeries.

The following parameters were compared:

- A. To study the effectiveness of transverses abdominis plane block for post-operative analgesia in Abdominal Surgeries.
- B. To compare the duration of analgesia and its effectiveness conferred by 0.25% Ropivacaine and 0.25% Bupivacaine.
- C. Total requirement of rescue analgesia.
- D. To watch for occurrence of side effects, if any.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This comparative clinical study was carried out in the Dept. of Aneesthesiology, S.C.L. general hospital, Gujarat. The study protocol was explained to each potential subject and written informed consent was obtained prior to the commencement of any procedure.

STUDY DESIGN:

A comparative clinical study was carried out on 60 adult patients belonging to ASA grade I or II, scheduled for elective abdominal Surgeries. Detailed history and preoperative assessment were carried out before operation. A detailed general as well as systemic examination was done to rule out any major systemic illness.

STUDY POPULATION:

A prospective, randomized controlled study was conducted on 60 subjects. All patients were administered spinal anaesthesia with bupivacaine heavy 0.5%, 2.0-4.0 ml with 25 G spinal needle at L2-L3 or L3-L4 vertebral interspace. The patients were randomly allocated in two

groups and study drug was injected at the end of surgery according to the group. The volume of administered drug kept constant (20 ml).

Group I: Patients received TAP BLOCK on each side with 10ml 0.25% Ropivacaine.

Group II: Patients received TAP BLOCK on each side with 10ml 0.25% Bupivacaine.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Age of patient-18 to 60yrs
- ASA (American Society of Anaesthesiologists) grade I, II
- Weight 40 - 80 kg

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patient's refusal
- Allergy to local anaesthetic agent
- Skin infections at the site of block
- Renal disease and psychiatric history
- Inability to comply with study assessment
- Patient on anticoagulants or bleeding disorder
- Underlying other significant systemic disease **Anaesthetic Protocol:**

Preoperatively patients were inquired about the NBM status. All patients were explained about the procedure and Visual Analogue Scale before taking written informed consent.

In pre-operative room pulse rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate and oxygen saturation were noted.

After securing intravenous line, all patients were preloaded with Inj. Ringer Lactate 10 – 15 ml/kg.

Patients were premedicated with inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.2mg IV and inj. Ondansetron 4mg IV half an hour before operation.

On operation table, baseline pulse, blood pressure, saturation of oxygen and ECG were recorded.

The patients were randomized in two groups.

Method of transversus abdominis plane block:

In supine position the lumbar triangle of Petit (formed anteriorly by External oblique muscle, posteriorly by Latissimus dorsi muscle and inferiorly by iliac crest)⁷ was identified. Under ultrasound guidance a 22-gauge, 5-8 cm long blunt tipped short bevelled needle was inserted in this triangle, just posterior to the mid-axillary line perpendicular to skin.⁸ A pop was felt when the needle passed through the fascial extensions of the external oblique muscle i.e., the tip was between the fascial layers of the external oblique muscle and the internal oblique muscle. A second pop indicated that the needle was in the fascial plane above the transversus abdominis muscle.⁹ 10 ml of the local anaesthetic solution was injected in this plane after negative aspiration. Same procedure repeated on other side.

Pain scores and vitals were evaluated every 30mins for 2hrs and then every 2 hours after surgery by an independent observer for pain at rest and on movement using visual analogy scale, time of first demand and total consumption for rescue analgesia, satisfaction with pain management and side-effects in both groups were noted. **In the postoperative period**, Inj. Tramadol 50 mg IV was given, when VAS>4 and repeated after 6 hours, when patient complained of pain persistently.

The time of first analgesic, total doses of analgesics within 48 postoperative hours and any side effects were also recorded.

Statistical analysis was done by using unpaired 't' test.

Visual Analogue scale (VAS) 10 points was used to assess post-operative analgesia.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

TABLE 1 – AGE, HEIGHT AND WEIGHT DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS

	Group A		Group B		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age (yrs.)	37.2	13.96	35.47	12.03	0.162
Height (cm)	157.6	5.5	158.57	5.13	0.912
Weight (kg)	62.77	5.39	62.4	5.15	0.672

There was no significant difference in mean age or mean height or mean weight among patients in both groups.

TABLE 2 - ASA PHYSICAL STATUS OF PATIENTS

ASA Grade		
Group	Grade – I	Grade - II
Group A	6	24
Group B	5	25

In group A, there were 6 patients of ASA grade I and 24 patients of ASA grade II and in group B, there were 5 patients of ASA grade I and 25 patients of ASA grade II.

TABLE 3 – DURATION OF SURGERY

Duration of surgery (min)				
Group	No. of patients	Mean	SD	p value
Group A	30	70.33	16.45	0.005
Group B	30	67.83	11.12	

In group A, mean duration of surgery was 70.33 ± 16.45 mins whereas in group B, it was 67.83 ± 11.12 mins. There was no statistically significant difference between two groups.

TABLE 4 – PREOPERATIVE VITALS

	Group A		Group B		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Pulse rate (/ min)	85.27	3.91	85	6.7	0.086
Systolic BP (mmHg)	116.67	13.21	118.8	8.65	0.033
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	75	7.31	76.47	5.05	0.025
Respiratory rate (/ min)	13.8	1.6	13.93	1.43	0.235

In group A, preoperative pulse was 85.27 ± 3.91 per min whereas in group B, it was 85.00 ± 6.70 per min.

In group A, systolic blood pressure was 116.67 ± 13.21 mmHg whereas in group B, it was 118.80 ± 8.65 mmHg.

In group A, diastolic blood pressure was 75.00 ± 7.31 mmHg whereas in group B, it was 76.47 ± 5.05 mmHg.

In group A, preoperative respiratory rate was 13.80 ± 1.60 per min whereas in group B, it was 13.93 ± 1.43 per min.

There was no significant difference hemodynamically in both groups.

TABLE 5 - MEAN PULSE RATE (PER MIN) AT DIFFERENT TIME INTERVALS AFTER TAP BLOCK

	Group A	Group B	p Value

	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Immediate after TAP Block	85.67	3.4	85.2	5.67	0.03
30 mins	84.73	4.15	84.87	4.83	0.814
2 hr	85.6	4.76	82.87	4.09	0.391
4 hr	84.53	4.23	83.07	3.95	0.45
6 hr	83.93	2.06	83.53	3.13	0.056
12 hr	85.67	3.64	82.93	4.25	0.094
24 hr	84.47	3.7	83.27	3.65	0.786

There was no significant difference of pulse rate at different time intervals from the time of performing the TAP block to 24 hrs in both groups.

TABLE 6 - MEAN SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE (MM OF HG) AT DIFFERENT TIME INTERVALS AFTER TAP BLOCK

	Group A		Group B		p Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Immediate after TAP Block	112	7.61	110.33	5.56	0.165
30 mins	112	8.05	110	7.42	0.466
2 hr	112.33	9.35	111.67	6.98	0.461
4 hr	111.67	8.33	112	6.64	0.731
6 hr	112.8	5.44	111.33	4.34	0.097
12 hr	113.33	8.84	111.33	5.07	0.648
24 hr	113	7.94	112	4.06	0.146

There was no significant difference of Systolic blood pressure at different time intervals from the time of performing the TAP block to 24 hr in both groups.

7 - MEAN DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE (MM OF HG) AT DIFFERENT TIME INTERVALS AFTER TAP BLOCK

	Group A		Group B		p-Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Immediate after TAP Block	72.33	4.3	72.33	5.04	0.833
30 mins	72	4.06	72.67	4.49	0.231
2 hr	73.33	6.06	71	4.02	0.184
4 hr	72.67	5.83	73.33	5.46	0.685
6 hr	72.33	5.04	73.67	5.56	0.067
12 hr	73.33	4.79	73.33	4.79	1
24 hr	72.67	4.49	73.33	4.79	0.273

There was no significant difference of Diastolic blood pressure at different time intervals from the time of performing the TAP block to 24hr in both groups.

TABLE 8- MEAN VISUAL ANALOGUE SCALE (VAS) SCORE AT DIFFERENT TIME INTERVALS IN BOTH GROUPS

	Group A		Group B		p Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
30 mins	0.23	0.56	1.23		0.002
2 hr	1.5	0.77	2	0.91	0.036
4 hr	1.87	1.25	2.8	0.66	0
6 hr	2.67	1.06	4.2	1.51	0.006
12 hr	3.2	0.96	0.81	1.17	0.185
24 hr	3.2	0.84	4.7	0.71	0.157

There was significant difference in Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) SCORE at different time intervals from the time of performing the TAP block to 30 mins, 2 hr, 4 hr and 6 hr in both groups.

At 30 mins Mean VAS Score was 0.23 in group A, whereas 1.23 in group B At 2 hr Mean VAS Score was 1.50 in group A, whereas 2.00 in group B.

At 4 hr Mean VAS Score was 1.87 in group A, whereas 2.80 in group B.

At 6 hr Mean VAS Score was 2.67 in group A, whereas 4.20 in group B.

There was no significant difference in VAS Score at 12 hr and 24 hr in both groups.

TABLE 9 – TOTAL DURATION OF ANALGESIA

Total duration of analgesia (hr)			
	Mean	SD	p-Value
Group A	9.3	1.46	<0.001
Group B	6.9	0.71	

The mean duration of analgesia was 9.3 ± 1.46 hr in Group A, where as in group B it was 6.9 ± 0.71 hr.

There was significant difference between mean duration of analgesia in both groups.

TABLE 10 - POSTOPERATIVE ANALGESIC CONSUMPTION IN 24 HOURS

Total duration of analgesia (mg)			
	Mean	SD	p Value
Group A	75	38.84	0.869
Group B	148.33	42.51	

The mean consumption of analgesic was 75.00 ± 38.84 mg tramadol in Group A and 148.33 ± 42.51 mg tramadol in Group B.

There was no significant difference between mean analgesic consumption in both groups.

TABLE 11 – ADVERSE EFFECTS IN BOTH GROUPS

Adverse effect	Group A		Group B		p value
	No.	%	No.	%	
Side effects of local anesthetic drugs	-	-	-	-	-
Hypotension	-	-	-	-	-
Bradycardia	-	-	-	-	-
Nausea	-	-	-	-	-
Vomiting	-	-	-	-	-
Hematoma	-	-	-	-	-

None of the patients in either group had any adverse effect.

DISCUSSION

The benefits of postoperative analgesia include reduction in postoperative stress response and postoperative morbidity, better surgical outcome, rehabilitation and rapid recovery, decreased incidence of side effects from analgesics, patient comfort and convenience.¹⁰

The TAP block is a simple and effective analgesic technique, appropriate for surgical procedures where parietal pain is a significant component of postoperative pain.¹¹ The local anaesthetics in TAP block have been demonstrated to provide excellent analgesia to the skin and musculature of the anterior abdominal wall.¹²

The principal finding of our study is that 0.25% Ropivacaine and 0.25% bupivacaine are equally effective in TAP block and provides effective postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing below umbilical surgeries under spinal anaesthesia. Our study data were comparable in both the groups in terms of demographic data, hemodynamic parameters, postoperative analgesia, VAS score, incidence of any side effects. We have found the superiority of TAP block in providing immediate postoperative analgesia reflected by a lower VAS score.

The most important clinical implication of our findings is the significant opioid sparing effects of TAP block in the postoperative period.¹³ Opioids, though very effective in perioperative pain management, may be associated with nausea, vomiting, pruritus, and respiratory depression. Moreover, some patients who are morbidly obese or having obstructive sleep apnoea will be maximally benefitted from TAP block as it provides opioid sparing effects.¹⁴ It may be a relatively safer alternative to neuraxial blocks for intra and postoperative analgesia in patients having coagulopathy.

CONCLUSION

We concluded that

- Transversus Abdominis Plane Block (TAP Block) provides better postoperative analgesia in various abdominal surgeries.
- 0.25% ropivacaine and 0.25% bupivacaine are equally effective in TAP block and provides effective postoperative analgesia but ropivacaine group shows longer duration of action compared to bupivacaine which was statistically significant without causing any increased adverse effects.
- Neither group has shown any side effects.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST: Nil

FUNDING: Nil

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: Nil